

ANALYSIS OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF UZBEK FOLKLORE

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The science of folklore is folklore studies, which examines the characteristics of folk art as an art of words, the stages of the emergence, formation and development of folklore, the laws of its creative process and way of life, its vital content, social nature, etc. discusses issues such as its artistic essence, artistic uniqueness, genre specification, as well as its interaction with written literature, connections and typology, poetics, method. A specialist dealing with the science of folklore is called a folklorist.

Folklore works in connection with sociology, ethnography, linguistics, literary studies, history, art studies, musicology and other disciplines. Because folklore as a syncretic word art is closely connected with all types of art.

Although folklore works in close connection with the science of literature, there are differences between them. For example, the ideological-aesthetic analysis of folklore works is carried out according to the laws of folklore studies, while the analysis of fiction is carried out in accordance with the laws of literary studies. In this case, a literary critic has clear and ready-made material related to the problem he is studying, but a folklorist does not have such an opportunity. He begins by collecting material from the people related to the problem he is studying. The peculiarity and difficulty of this process is that it requires the folklorist to engage in long-term collecting activities. He should pay attention to the relevance of this or that folklore work to a certain ceremony, the melody, the presence of theatrical elements, the liveliness of the language. For this, the collector must be aware of the knowledge in these areas.

The science of folklore consists of three branches:

1. Collecting samples of folk art. Folklore studies, first of all, begins with recording (collecting) examples of folk art. This process is carried out in the form of individual, personal initiative and collectively organized scientific expedition.
2. Publication of collected examples of folk art. This field is called folklore textology (textology). At the same time, the variants of this or that folklore work are mixed, and special attention is paid to choosing the ideal and artistically perfect ones, to fully and perfectly preserving the features of live performance of each work, to ensure the naturalness of the language, characteristic of live expression. Uzbek folklore has accumulated rich experience in this field. Ergash

Jumanbulbul's son's five-volume "Nightingale Taronalari" in Uzbek and three-volume "Pesnya Bulbulya" in Russian, as well as the fifty-volume "Uzbek Folk Art" series, are serious examples of this experience. are the results.

3. Researching folk art. It is known that folk songs are connected with melody, a certain part of them is performed in harmony with dance, Folklorist cooperates with musicologists and choreographers in order to comprehensively study these features.

Folklore works deeply reflect folk traditions and customs. In this respect, the genres of ritual folklore are distinguished. In researching these processes, the folklorist relies on ethnography, otherwise, his research will be one-sided.

If the uniqueness of the language of works of folk art is studied in cooperation with dialectology (dialectology), folk pedagogy (ethnopedagogy) reflected in these works works in cooperation with scientific pedagogy. Thus, just as folklore is unique, the science about it - folklore studies - is also unique.

The role and importance of folklore in ensuring the maturity of society, the depth of social consciousness and the richness of the human spiritual world. That's why collecting folklore samples, studying them and putting them at the service of time, using them to justify one or another event has been relevant in all eras. Authors of historical, scientific and literary works have used folklore samples for various purposes, sometimes in a modified and reworked form, and in many cases, in the form of a meaningful statement. In this process, in a certain sense, the first experiments in recording folklore works can be seen. Folklore materials presented in the work "Devonu lug'otit turk" by the great scholar of the 11th century, Mahmud Kashgari, are an example of this.

The records of ancient world tourists and historians about legends and narratives, various customs and ceremonies, as well as this process, which began in the era of written stone inscriptions, continues to this day in various contents and forms, in connection with the nature of the historical development of literature and art. . In other words, after creation, folklore works continue to live in their natural conditions, in the process of oral performance, singing, speaking, playing, showing, spreading and "re-creating" in the second form. But their second form, that is, the appearance of folklore samples in historical and literary records, in the works of writers and composers - the history of folklorisms is not the history of recording and studying folk creativity. In this sense, the interest in Uzbek oral works for folkloristic purposes, their recording and study began in the second half of the 20th century.

Russian orientalists, tourists, and ambassadors who lived in the second half of the last century and the beginning of the 20th century were the official people of the tsarist administration who recorded, checked and published some examples of Uzbek folklore. There are important notes on his life, customs, and oral creativity: his impressions of folk games, clowns, curiosities, sayils, etc. are described; sometimes descriptions of oral dramas and some fairy tales are recorded. For example, A.A. Kushakevich "Farhod and Shirin", N. Lyapunova "Sweet Girl", A. Vasilev "Hirsitdin Polvan", "Prince Nazar Muhammad and Princess Nazar's Bibi", A.N. Samoylovich "Grandpa Annamurad", "The husband who married who published the fairy tales "wife". A.F. Eichhorn and V.V. Leysek recorded folk tunes.

From the same period, some examples of Uzbek folklore began to be known on a world scale. The services of the Hungarian scientist and tourist H. Vambery are great in this. He published more than a hundred folk proverbs, excerpts from the epic "Yusuf bilan Ahmad" together with the Uzbek text in the "Chigatoy Language Textbook" published in Leipzig in 1867. In 1911, he managed to publish the Khorezm version of Yusuf bilan Ahmad in its entirety.

In the 19th century, on the initiative of some folklore and book lovers, as well as Bakhshis, some handwritten copies of folk epics began to appear, and they were widely distributed among the people through copying, and later, typographic and lithographic publishing. Such publications resulted from the translation or processing of folk epics and fairy tales. Among these works are "Hikyati Gorogli sultan", "Yusufbek and Ahmadbek", "Tulumbi", "Chor dar vesh", "Rustami epic", "Tahir and Zuhra", "Ashiq Gharib and Shokhsanam". , "Sanobar", "Boz'glan", "Bakhrom and Gulandom", "Dilorom", "Hurliqo and Hamro", "Gulfarah", "Boz yigit", "Aldarkosa" and others. can be shown. But these publications were at a much lower level than from the point of view of Russian and European science of that time, and were far from the requirements of folklore studies. Although modern science (V.V. Radlov, Ch. Valikhanov, A.A. Divaev and others) has made some progress in the study of the epics of the Kazakh, Kyrgyz and Karakalpak peoples, the epic creativity of the Uzbek people has been neglected. This situation caused Uzbek folklore with all its richness and originality to remain unknown to science in the period before the Russian Revolution. After 1920, the work of collecting and studying Uzbek folk art on a scientific basis began intensively, already in the first years of that period, the work of collecting and using Uzbek artistic and musical folklore Republic of Turkestan Public Education Commissariat was assigned to the Scientific Department (Scientific Council,

State Scientific Council). As a result, in 1918, a short collection of Uzbek folk art was published in the 1st issue of the "Ma'rif" magazine. In it, materials related to all genres of Uzbek folklore were collected and sent to the editorial office. For the first time in the history of Uzbek epicology, Fazil Yoldosh recorded a part of the epic "Alpomish" from his son and Hamrokul Bakhshi. As a result of his expedition, he wrote an article entitled "The work of acquaintance among Uzbeks" and published it in the newspaper "Turkiston" (December 18, 1922). The article discusses for the first time about the highest examples of Uzbek epic: "Alpomish", "Goroghli", "Yusuf-Akhmad". The researcher compares the epic "Alpomish" with the famous "Odyssey" and "Iliad". G. O. Yunusov published some excerpts from the epic "Alpomish" written by him in the magazine "Bilim Uchogi" (1923) with a short introduction. In 1921-1922, Ghulam Zafari recorded various songs, lapars, oral drama works during his trips to the Fergana valley, Elbek, Tashkent region, and about puppeteers and amateurs. These actions were a serious step forward in drawing the attention of the scientific and literary community to the work of truly studying the folklore, language and ethnography of the Uzbek people. The son of Ergash Jumanbulbul, the son of Fazil Yoldosh, the son of Muhammadqul Jonmirod, and the son of such talented people's artists were identified. In a short period of time, "Alpomish", "Yodgor", "Shaybani Khan", "Yusuf with Ahmed", "Alibek with Bolibek", "Rustam", "Goroghalin", "Yunus Fairy", "Misqol Fairy", Great works such as "Gulnor Pari", "Avaz Khan", "Hasan Khan", "Dalli", "Ravshan", "Hasan Batrak" were recorded. The identification and penning of such a large-scale amazing epic product demonstrated the extraordinary richness of Uzbek folklore.

F. M. Karomatov, M. Kh. Kadirov, M. S. Saidov, M. Murodov, T. Mirzaev, B. Sarimsakov, K. Imomov led the expedition. As a result, a very large archive of folklore was created in Uzbekistan and is getting richer every day. Young Uzbek folklorists made original observations regarding folk artists as creators, that epic works should be studied directly in connection with the place where they are sung, the conditions and the singer himself. They put forward the idea. At a time when there were fluctuations in the evaluation of the creative talent of the people, that is, the second half of the 20s, it was of great methodological and methodological importance. This methodologically correct approach to folk art is clearly visible in the articles of Hadi Zarif (1905-1972) about folk gifts.

Another characteristic characteristic of the period of formation of folklore studies of the Uzbek people is the attention paid to the development of folklore textual studies. In addition to collecting and studying his work, it is necessary to

publish and present it again. In this case, the epic "Alla" recorded by Ghazi Alim's son Ergash Jumanbulbul and "Shaybani Khan" narrated by Polkan can be shown as examples. These publications are distinguished by the fact that they are published for the first time and have a thorough scientific basis. Thus, in the second half of the twenties, Uzbek folklore had its own scientific direction, and its foundation was created.

In 1935, the book "Materials for the History of Uzbek Theater" by Miyonbuzruk Salihov was published. In this book, the author rightly describes the dramatic plays of those who are interested in the nature, essence, and types of folk theater as "the most characteristic and perfect among folk stage plays, in which all importance is given to appearance, movement and words." evaluates. He adds the book "Sarkardalar" to the book. This book of the scientist has great value in the history of folklore studies from the point of view of publishing folklore works and some comments.

As a result of the attention paid to folklore, the rise to the level of teaching Uzbek folklore as an independent course in the philology faculties of higher educational institutions increased the need for manuals and textbooks in this field even more.

For this reason, "Uzbek Folklore" (Book 1, 1939) was published for higher educational institutions. This christology compiled by Hadi Zarif was the result of great research and important scientific conclusions. It reflects a general view of folklore as a whole course, which was achieved through in-depth observation of all samples and their scientific analysis. In the second half of the 1930s, Mansur Afzalov, Sharifa Abdullaeva, and Yusuf Sultanov entered Uzbek folklore. Gafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Maqsud Sheikhzadeh, Shakir Sulaiman, Sharif Reza and other writers are engaged in folklore.

Mansur Afzalov (1910-1973), the famous Uzbek folk poet Islam Nazar, worked with them for many years, diligently studied his repertoire and creativity. He first announced the results of his research in the article "Son of Islamic poet Nazar oglu". He recorded the poet's epic "Orzigul" and published it in 1941. M.Afzalov, in the article "Uzbek Folklore" written together with B.Karimov, followed in the footsteps of Hodi Zarif, who for the first time thoroughly examined the folklore of the Uzbek people, and put an end to its fifteen-year development.

During these years, folklorist Buyuk Karimov (1916-1945) also carried out effective research on Uzbek folk tales. In 1919, he published "Uzbek Folk Tales", the researcher's observations about Uzbek folk tales and fairy tales were placed

at the beginning of the book, which became of great importance for Uzbek folklore. The author, although controversial, classified the fairy tales to some extent and made a thematic analysis. This book was the first large collection of fairy tales.

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